

spectra (CDCl_3) in general showed aromatic multiplets in the range δ 6.80 - .60 (Table 1).

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Synthesis of Some Pyrimidinylpyrazoles and Pyrimidinyl-2-Pyrazoline-5-Ones

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PYRAZOLES are known to possess various types of biological activity¹⁻³. Arylazo derivatives of pyrazoles have been prepared earlier in these laboratories as possible antidiabetic agents^{4,5}. In view of the important pharmacological activity displayed by the pyrimidine derivatives, it was thought of considerable interest to prepare the compounds containing both the pyrimidine and pyrazole nucleus. The present communication describes the synthesis of various 3,5-disubstituted-1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-4-arylazopyrazoles (I, II and III) and 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3-methyl-4-arylhydrazono-2-pyrazoline-5-ones (IV).

The condensation of 2-hydrazino-4,6-dimethylpyrimidine⁶ with 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones⁴, 1-phenylbutane-1,2,3-trione-2-arylhydrazones⁷ and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,2,3-trione-2-arylhydrazones in glacial acetic acid-ethanol gave 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles(I). (Table 1),

TABLE 1 - 4-ARYLAZO-(4,6-DIMETHYL PYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3,5-DIMETHYL-PYRAZOLES(I)

[I], R₁ = R₂ = CH₃,
[II], R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = C₆H₅,
[III], R₁ = R₂ = C₆H₅,

Compound No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C
1	Hydrogen	50	98 ^a
2	2-Chloro	65	142 ^d
3	3-Chloro	65	112 ^c
4	2-Methyl	60	150 ^d
5	4-Methyl	70	160 ^b
6	2-Methoxy	55	136 ^d
7	2-Ethoxy	60	178 ^c
8	4-Ethoxy	60	89 ^d
9	4-Bromo	70	114 ^f
10	2,5-Dimethyl	70	142 ^d
11	3-Nitro	65	108 ^d

a, red; b, light yellow; c, yellow; d, brown; e, orange yellow; f, light greenish yellow.

The nitrogen analysis of all the compounds is consistent with the respective composition.

TABLE 2 - 4-ARYLAZO-1-(4,6-DIMETHYLPYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3-METHYL-5-PHENYLPYRAZOLES(II)

Compound No.	R	Yield %	mp. °C
1	Hydrogen	70	154
2	2-Chloro	60	207 ^e
3	3-Chloro	55	170 ^c
4	2-Methyl	50	155 ^e
5	2-Methoxy	50	208 ^c
6	3-Methoxy	45	142 ^d
7	4-Ethoxy	55	120 ^d
8	2,3-Dimethyl	60	267 ^d
9	2,5-Dimethyl	60	110 ^d
10	2,5-Dichloro	65	178 ^c

* See footnote Table 1.

TABLE 3—4-ARYLAZO-1-(4,6-DIMETHYLPYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3,5-DIPHENYL-PYRAZOLES(III)

Compound No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C
1	Hydrogen	50	145 ^c
2	2-Chloro	55	180 ^e
3	3-Chloro	60	210 ^o
4	2-Methyl	50	198 ^d
5	3-Methyl	55	178 ^e
6	2-Methoxy	50	125 ^a
7	3-Methoxy	50	146 ^d
8	2-Ethoxy	50	210 ^o
9	4-Ethoxy	60	185 ^o
10	2,3-Dimethyl	65	205 ^e

* See foot note Table 1.

TABLE 4—4-ARYLHYDRAZONO-1-(4,6-DIMETHYLPYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3-METHYLPYRAZOLINE-5-ONES(IV)

Compound No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C
1	Hydrogen	75	204 ^a
2	2-Chloro	60	205 ^o
3	3-Chloro	65	113 ^b
4	4-Chloro	70	201 ^o
5	2-Methyl	60	183 ^b
6	3-Methyl	65	180 ^o
7	4-Methyl	60	154 ^o
8	2-Methoxy	55	220 ^o
9	4-Methoxy	50	178 ^e
10	3-Bromo	60	216 ^o
11	4-Bromo	70	102 ^o
12	4-Fluoro	65	204 ^o
13	2-Nitro	65	172 ^d
14	3-Nitro	55	215 ^o
15	4-Nitro	70	218 ^o
16	2,6-Dichloro	75	168 ^o

* See foot note Table 1.

1-(4, 6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3-methyl-5-phenyl-4-arylazopyrazoles(II), (Table 2), 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3,5-diphenyl-4-arylazopyrazoles (III), (Table 3) respectively in good yields(45-70%). In a similar way, the condensation of 2-hydrazin-4,6-dimethylpyrimidine with ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-arylhyaazones⁶ resulted in the formation of 1-(4, 6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3-methyl-4-arylhyaazono-2-pyrazoline-5-ones (IV), (Table 4) in good yields (50 – 75%). Some selected compounds have been assayed for the antidiabetic activity by the procedure described earlier⁸. None of the compounds showed any noteworthy activity.

1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3,5, dimethyl-4-phenyl-azopyrazole(I, 1) :

A solution of 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-phenylhydrazone (2.04g, 0.01 mole) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was added to a hot solution of 2-hydrazino-4,6-dimethylpyrimidine (1.38g, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (50 ml). The resulting mixture was heated at reflux for 3 hr. It was cooled. The crystals of (I, 1) obtained were crystallized from dimethylformamide. Yield : 1.5g, 50%; m.p. 98^o ; Found : C, 66.20 ; H, 5.58 ; N, 27.30 ; C₁₇H₁₈N₆ requires C, 66.66 ; H, 5.88 ; N, 27.45%.

1-(4, 6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3-methyl-4-phenylhydrazone-2-pyrazoline-5-ones(IV, 1) :

A solution of ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-phenylhydrazone (2.36g, 0.01 mole) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was added to hot solution of 2-hydrazino-4, 6-dimethylpyrimidine (2.76 g, 0.02 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) with stirring. The resulting mixture was heated at reflux for 2 hr. On cooling crystals separated out which were crystallized from dimethylformamide. Yield : 2.3g, 75%, m.p. 204^o ; Found : C, 62.00 ; H, 4.90 ; N, 27.40. C₁₆H₁₆N₆O requires C,62.33 ; H, 5.19 ; N, 27.27%.

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